

Aerodynamic Performance of Various Strut-Braced Wing Designs for Distributed Electric Propulsion Configurations in Forward Flights

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Strut-braced wing (SBW) configurations incorporating leading-edge-mounted distributed electric propulsion (DEP) systems have been investigated for next-generation aircraft applications worldwide. This arrangement combines the aerodynamic and structural advantages of the SBW design with the low-emission potential of the distributed propulsion system, while the presence of the strut and the interaction with the DEP system substantially modify the aerodynamic characteristics relative to conventional configurations. This study aims to investigate the aerodynamic performance of different strut-braced DEP designs under various operating conditions. Three different strut designs and five DEP propeller arrangements are considered, with varying wing-strut joint locations positioned either between the propellers or behind the mid propeller location of different triple-propeller leading-edge-mounted DEP configurations. The experimental results show that the shortest strut design (Strut A) significantly reduces wing drag, achieving values lower than those of the corresponding no-strut wing configuration in most studied cases. The drag reduction is more pronounced at lower propeller rotational speeds, with improvements of up to 30% observed for the most effective DEP configuration. Among the five propeller arrangements investigated, the configuration of one centrally mounted 15-inch propeller and two adjacent 12-inch propellers provides the most favourable aerodynamic performance, yielding the highest lift-to-drag ratio for the strut-braced DEP configurations. Numerical simulations using an Euler-based actuator-disk method with adaptive mesh refinement were conducted to validate and further investigate the experimental findings. The numerical predictions successfully reproduced the drag reduction observed for the Strut A design compared to the no-strut wing configuration, with a consistent drag-reduction region identified in the strut-braced area.

I. Nomenclature

C_D	=	propeller drag coefficient
C_L	=	propeller lift coefficient
C_P	=	surface pressure coefficient
$C_{P,\text{prop}}$	=	propeller power coefficient
C_T	=	propeller thrust coefficient
c_{strut}	=	strut chord length

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c_{wing}	=	wing chord length
D	=	propeller diameter
J	=	propeller advance ratio
n	=	revolutions per second
P	=	propeller power
P/D	=	propeller pitch-to-diameter ratio
S	=	reference wing area
t/c	=	thickness-to-chord ratio
T	=	propeller thrust
V_{∞}	=	freestream velocity
\vec{S}_{act}	=	actuator body-force vector
α	=	wing angle of attack
Λ	=	sweep angle
μ	=	dynamic viscosity
ρ	=	air density
AD	=	actuator disk
AMR	=	adaptive mesh refinement
AoA	=	angle of attack
BEMT	=	blade element momentum theory
CCW	=	counter-clockwise
DEP	=	distributed electric propulsion
ESC	=	electronic speed controller
JST	=	Jameson–Schmidt–Tukel scheme
MS-DEP	=	mixed-size DEP
MTOM	=	maximum take-off mass
RANS	=	Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes
rpm	=	revolutions per minute
SA	=	Spalart–Allmaras turbulence model
SBW	=	strut-braced wing
URANS	=	Unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes
US-DEP	=	uniformly sized DEP
VLM	=	vortex lattice method

II. Introduction

Long-term environmental objectives are becoming central to modern aircraft design, aiming to maximise performance and energy efficiency while addressing the pressing environmental challenges of today’s aviation industry. Flightpath 2050 exemplifies these ambitions, setting targets of a 75% reduction in CO_2 emissions and a 90% reduction in NO_X emissions by 2050 [1]. Consequently, the development of novel airframe and propulsion technologies remains a top priority. Popular research topics with such goals include developing various electric propulsion architectures with more efficient and sustainable aviation technologies [2].

One potential candidate for efficient aircraft designs featuring electric propulsion is the distributed electric propulsion (DEP) configuration. DEP systems typically employ multiple smaller propellers, dividing the total thrust, thereby reducing noise emissions and improving overall aircraft aerodynamic performance. Worldwide researchers are dedicated to both aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics of the DEP concept, examining both aspects numerically and experimentally [3–16]. To date, DEP systems with leading-edge-mounted propellers have demonstrated their ability to enhance aircraft aerodynamic efficiency [3–10]. Moore and Ning [4] conducted a numerical investigation into the effects of various DEP design parameters such as propeller number, diameter, and tip speed on overall aircraft performance, including total thrust, wing lift coefficient, and take-off roll distance. The propeller performance was modelled using blade element momentum theory (BEMT), while a vortex lattice method (VLM) was employed to analyse wing aerodynamics across different DEP configurations. They found that the optimised eight-propeller configuration could significantly reduce the take-off distance by up to 80% compared to the baseline two-propeller case, with a 36% reduction in take-off speed. Ma et al. [7] recently developed a wing–propeller interaction model to compare the aerodynamic performance of conventional single-propeller configurations with DEP setups featuring up to four

propellers per semi-span. Their results showed that the DEP configuration achieved approximately a 6% increase in aircraft range compared to the conventional setup, with the four-propeller arrangement exhibiting significantly reduced induced drag as the tip-mounted propeller effectively counteracted the wingtip vortex. Han et al. [9] experimentally investigated a series of leading-edge-mounted DEP systems, comparing dual and triple propeller configurations. Their results revealed that the triple-propeller arrangement significantly improved overall wing aerodynamic performance in terms of lift-to-drag ratio compared to the dual-propeller setup, while also achieving lower noise emissions.

While the DEP configuration has proven its effectiveness in improving the aerodynamic efficiency of the aircraft, directly increasing the wingspan will also dramatically reduce the induced drag caused by the wingtip vortices [17, 18], hence further enhancing the aerodynamic performance. Due to structural and ICAO regulation constraints, aircraft with strut-braced wing (SBW) configurations are also of great interest [17–24]. The strut of the SBW aircraft can reduce the maximum wing bending moment by as much as 50%, resulting in a substantial decrease in wing weight [17, 19, 20]. Sanchez Barreda [18] compared and discussed different SBW aircraft configurations with an optimised Airbus A320 aircraft in his work. It was found that SBW aircraft with high wing aspect ratio and folding wingtips have substantial effectiveness in improving the aircraft’s maximum lift-to-drag ratio, by approximately 30% compared to the optimised A320 aircraft. Sohst et al. [22] also performed a numerical analysis on the aerodynamic performance of a high aspect ratio strut-braced wing with wing aspect ratio $AR = 21.2$ and compared it with a conventional wing with AR of 12. The optimisation results indicated that although the wing mass increased compared to the baseline wing, the maximum take-off mass (MToM) achieved by the SBW configuration increased by 3.5%, and also achieved a 17.2% improvement in lift-to-drag ratio compared to the baseline conventional wing. Apart from the SBW wing analysis alone, Gilbrook et al. [24] also discussed the performance of leading-edge-mounted propeller DEP aircraft with high-aspect-ratio SBW. They concluded that distributed propulsion with SBW has the potential to further increase the aircraft’s lift-to-drag ratio through wing-propeller interaction modelling, offering at least 6% additional energy efficiency. They also noted that the gains of distributed propulsion were observed during climb and descent, rather than in the cruise phase of the flight, where higher lift is essential.

With the existing literature mainly examining the strut design of the SBW aircraft from structural and aeroelastic perspectives, there are few investigations of the aerodynamic effects of strut positions relative to that of the propellers on the wing, especially from an experimental standpoint. Therefore, this work aims to experimentally and numerically study the aerodynamic performance of the overall DEP system across different strut designs and leading-edge-mounted triple-propeller DEP configurations, with different propeller arrangements. Experimental work was carried out in the Lawson Wind Tunnel Laboratory at the University of Bristol, while numerical simulations were conducted at the University of Strathclyde, Glasgow. This paper is structured as follows: Section III describes the experimental setup for the DEP and SBW configurations and the test matrix used in this study, along with the numerical setup for the simulations. Section IV presents experimental observations and discussions, while the numerical results and flow field visualisations are illustrated and analysed in the following Section V. Finally, Section VI summarises the key findings and provides potential future work based on this current study.

III. Methodology

A. Experimental setup.

In this section, the experimental setup and test cases are described. First, the DEP setup in the wind tunnel and the nomenclature for the different DEP configurations used in this work are introduced, followed by a demonstration of various strut designs. Finally, test cases that had been carried out are defined towards the end of this subsection.

1. DEP test rig setup.

The strut-braced DEP configurations were tested in the Low-Speed Wind Tunnel at the University of Bristol. This is a closed-loop wind tunnel with an octagonal test section measuring 2.1 m by 1.5 m (7 ft by 5 ft), and a maximum test wind speed of 60 m/s. The facility is equipped with an ATE AEROTECH AID-010-12394-A six-component overhead balance installed directly above the test section, and it is capable of measuring wing lift, drag, side forces, and the corresponding pitch, yaw, and roll moments. This ensures accurate characterisation of the aerodynamic forces and moments acting on the wing. The overhead balance also functioned as a turntable, allowing the wing to rotate to different angles of attack (AoAs) during the test.

The rectangular wing was designed using the NACA 0018 aerofoil profile, with a chord length of $c_{\text{wing}} = 464$ mm

Fig. 1 Schematics of front views of the US-DEP configurations: (a) 12–12–12 configuration, (b) 15–15–15 configuration, and (c) side view of 12–12–12 configuration. All propellers are spinning CCW when viewed from the front. Dimensions shown in mm.

Fig. 2 Schematics of front views of the MS-DEP configurations: (a) 15–12–12 configuration, (b) 12–15–12 configuration, and (c) 12–12–15 configuration. 15-inch propellers are highlighted in red; all propellers are spinning CCW when viewed from the front.

and a semi-span of 1350 mm. The wing was primarily fabricated via 3D printing using materials including Nylon 12, PLA, and clear resin. This study investigated five leading-edge-mounted, triple-propeller DEP configurations: namely, the 12–12–12, 15–15–15, 15–12–12, 12–15–12, and 12–12–15 configuration. Here, “12” and “15” denote the propeller diameters in inches. Both the 12-inch and 15-inch propellers were five-bladed designs, sharing identical twist and normalised chord distributions along the normalised radial positions. Both propellers employed the Clark-Y aerofoil profile and had a pitch-to-diameter ratio of $P/D = 1$. The nomenclature of the DEP configurations followed the definition of the inboard–mid–outboard propeller sequence. Accordingly, the 12–12–12 configuration represented three uniformly sized 12-inch propellers, whereas the 15–12–12 configuration represented an inboard 15-inch propeller combined with two 12-inch propellers at the mid and outboard positions, and so forth. The propeller arrangements were categorised into two sets: uniformly sized DEP (US-DEP) configurations and mixed-sized DEP (MS-DEP) configurations. The US-DEP configurations consisted of propellers with identical diameters (12–12–12 and 15–15–15), whereas the MS-DEP configurations consisted of propellers with varying diameters (15–12–12, 12–15–12, and 12–12–15). For all configurations, the nacelle positions on the wing were fixed; thus, the propeller hub-to-hub distance remained constant across all cases. All propellers were co-rotating in the counter-clockwise (CCW) direction when viewed from the front.

The schematics of the US-DEP and MS-DEP configurations are illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively.

Each propeller installed in the configurations mentioned above was driven by a propulsion unit comprising a brushless DC motor, an electronic speed controller (ESC), a laser tachometer, and a load cell. The setup utilised T-MOTOR AT7215 30CC KV270 brushless motors paired with T-MOTOR AT115A6-14S ESC units. Precise control of the propeller rotational speed was achieved using a closed-loop PID controller implemented in-house in National Instruments LabVIEW, which received real-time RPM feedback from a Monarch 6180-029 ROLS-P laser tachometer located outside the wind-tunnel test section. Thrust measurements were obtained using three Futek MBA 500 biaxial load cells equipped with six Futek IAA 100 channel amplifiers, with each of the amplifiers responsible for one force or one moment channel for all three propellers. Prior to testing, all load cells were correctly calibrated using a series of known weights and zeroed before and after each run. For consistency, a sanity check was also conducted by placing each load cell in the same position within the tunnel under identical flow conditions with the same propeller. This allowed any systematic error associated with the load cells to be eliminated. Propeller thrust and torque data were acquired using a National Instruments PXIe-01926Q chassis with three PXIe-6341 modules and recorded in MATLAB at a consistent sampling rate over 16 seconds.

2. Strut designs.

Fig. 3 Schematics of front views of different strut designs with the 12–12–12 configuration. From left to right: Strut A design, Strut B design, and Strut C design. All propellers are spinning CCW when viewed from the front. Dimensions shown in mm.

Three different strut designs were applied to each of the five DEP configurations mentioned above. These strut designs are shown in Fig. 3 with the 12–12–12 configuration, namely Strut A, Strut B and Strut C. All struts were mounted on a large circular endplate, and positioned 256 mm below the main DEP wing. The struts were manufactured using PLA and clear resin 3D printing, with the NACA 0020 symmetric aerofoil shape and a constant chord length $c_{strut} = 186$ mm, corresponding to 40% of c_{wing} and 0° in sweep. The aerofoil selection is based on [17, 21], where the thickness-to-chord ratio t/c of the strut to the main wing can be obtained as:

$$(t/c)_{strut} = (t/c)_{wing} + \frac{0.05}{\cos(\Lambda)}, \quad (1)$$

where t/c is the aerofoil thickness-to-chord ratio and Λ represents the wing sweep angle, but the t/c ratio of the strut should not exceed 20%. The distance between the leading edge of the strut and wing was 110 mm, and the spar of the strut was mounted at around 37% of the main wing chord c_{wing} . The blended joints of all the struts were designed as

circular-arc sections with a 120 mm diameter, connected to a vertical section of 27 mm between the blended joint and the wing. Strut A was the shortest strut design, installed at the mid-point between the inboard and the mid propeller. Strut B was placed directly behind the mid propeller, with the inboard 12-inch propeller slipstream further away from the strut surface. Strut C was the longest design, installed between the mid- and outboard propellers. The centreline of the strut aerofoil (when viewed from the front) of the Strut C design was directly on the edge of the mid 12-inch propeller diameter (as shown on the right in Fig. 3). Moreover, the aerodynamic performance of all US-DEP and MS-DEP configurations without a strut mounted on the wing was also tested to enable comparisons between configurations with and without the strut. Figure 4 illustrates the 3D view of the 12–12–12 configuration with Strut C design and its installation inside the octagonal test section of the wind tunnel.

Fig. 4 3D view and installation inside the wind tunnel of the 12–12–12 configuration with strut C design. Dimension shown in mm.

3. Testing cases.

To enable consistent aerodynamic comparisons across all five DEP configurations, the overall thrust produced by the three propellers was matched across all configurations at $\alpha = 0^\circ$. Two different testing cases were established for the current study, as outlined in Table 1. For Case 1, all 12-inch propellers were spinning at 4000 rpm, whereas the rotational speeds of the 15-inch propellers were lower at 2675 rpm due to their larger diameters. In Case 2, the rotational speed of the 12-inch propellers increased to 6500 rpm, while the 15-inch propellers spun at 4125 rpm. Higher propeller rotational speeds result in higher slipstream speeds behind the propellers, and therefore, the interaction between the flow and the strut will be different. For both cases, the inflow speeds were set to $V_\infty = 10$ m/s, with wing AoA α sweeping from -8° to 20° .

B. Numerical setup.

This section outlines the numerical methodology adopted to investigate the aerodynamic interaction between the distributed propulsion system and the strut-braced wing configuration in the current study. First, the Euler-based computational framework is introduced. Next, the actuator-disk methodology used to model the distributed propellers is described, followed by the adaptive mesh refinement procedure employed to improve slipstream and wake resolution while maintaining computational efficiency.

Table 1 Testing cases for US-DEP and MS-DEP configurations with different strut designs.

Case	Inflow speed V_{inf} (m/s)	Wing AoA sweep	Propeller rotational speeds (rpm)	
			12-inch	15-inch
Case 1	10	-8° to 20°	4000	2675
Case 2	10	-8° to 20°	6500	4125

1. Euler Methodology.

The numerical analysis was conducted with the open-source Stanford University Unstructured (SU2) software [25]. For this study, an Euler approach was used rather than RANS, with analysis conducted under inviscid, steady-flow assumptions. Consequently, no turbulence closure model was applied and viscous stresses, heat conduction, boundary-layer development, and skin-friction drag were not resolved. The Euler approach was attractive for this study as a method to isolate the inviscid aerodynamic performance and rapidly investigate aerodynamic coupling between the strut and the wing. The Euler strategy effectively served as a low-cost, low-fidelity analysis tool, providing preliminary insights. Convective fluxes were discretised using the second-order Jameson–Schmidt–Turkel (JST) scheme with scalar artificial dissipation to stabilise gradients, while spatial gradients were reconstructed using a Green–Gauss least-squares procedure, ensuring nominal second-order spatial accuracy. The computational mesh was generated using Gmsh [26], forming an initial mesh with refined regions necessary for the modelling of the propellers.

The Euler methodology aims to capture lift, pressure drag, and inviscid propulsion–airframe coupling, but it does not account for viscous drag, boundary-layer separation, wall shear stress, or turbulence-induced losses. These limitations are considered when interpreting aerodynamic performance relative to the experimental results.

2. Actuator Disk Methodology.

The aerodynamic effects of the distributed propulsion system were modelled using a steady actuator disk (AD) approach within SU2. The method avoided the need for physical propellers and instead utilised a disk-shaped region that imparted momentum and energy to the flow through volumetric source terms. This approach reproduced the mean aerodynamic influence of the propellers without resolving the rotating blades, making it well-suited to distributed and hybrid-electric propulsion studies. Within the RANS framework, the actuator disk introduces additional momentum sources in the governing equations:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \bar{F}^c(U) - \nabla \cdot \bar{F}^v(U, \nabla U) - S_{act} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where S_{act} is the actuator body-force vector representing both axial and tangential contributions. The total thrust and torque are prescribed using classical momentum theory through the thrust and power coefficients C_T and $C_{P,prop}$, and the advance ratio J , defined as:

$$C_T = \frac{T}{\rho n^2 D^4}, C_{P,prop} = \frac{P}{\rho n^3 D^5}, J = \frac{V_\infty}{nD} \quad (3)$$

where V_∞ is the freestream velocity, n the rotational speed, D the propeller diameter, T the thrust, ρ the air density, and P the power. With these governing equations, the propeller behaviour can be fully defined using known input parameters and target radial distributions of thrust and power.

When utilising the source term methodology for actuator modelling, the actuator region was prescribed directly into the mesh as a dense element region rather than as a boundary surface. Each disk was defined by its centre, radius, and orientation. The intersecting elements were identified and assigned a projected area proportional to their intersection with the disk plane. Scaling factors ensured that the integrated thrust and torque equalled the prescribed propeller operating conditions, maintaining total momentum and energy addition independent of mesh density. This implementation captured the mean aerodynamic coupling between the propeller slipstreams and the airframe while avoiding the computational cost of fully resolved blade simulations. It enabled an accurate representation of propeller–wing interactions and induced downwash effects, which are critical for hybrid-electric and distributed propulsion studies.

3. Mesh Adaptation.

To balance computational efficiency and physical accuracy, all simulations employed anisotropic adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) within SU2. The AMR algorithm automatically refined and coarsened the grid according to a Mach-number-gradient sensor, ensuring that additional resolution was concentrated near the actuator disks and within the developing slipstreams while maintaining coarser spacing in the far field. During each AMR cycle, the mesh was regenerated to cluster nodes in regions of strong flow gradients, particularly in the shear layers trailing each actuator disk [27].

This refinement approach eliminated the need for manually generated multi-resolution meshes and prevented excessive cell counts that would otherwise accompany uniform refinement. As the actuator forces were applied as body forces scaled by the local control-volume size, the total thrust and torque remained conserved throughout mesh adaptation. Consequently, aerodynamic coefficients such as lift, drag, and thrust remained invariant once the actuator region was adequately resolved.

Fig. 5 Resulting meshes: un-adapted (Left) and adapted (Right).

The use of AMR ensured grid-independent solutions with efficient resource utilisation. It provided a robust means of improving wake resolution and flow-feature fidelity whilst preserving the highly refined region required for the source term actuator-disk methodology to be applied appropriately. Figure 5 shows a concise example of the AMR process being applied to a strut-braced wing test case.

IV. Experimental results.

This section presents the experimental results for all US- and MS-DEP configurations with each strut design. First, the wing lift and drag polars, together with the aerodynamic efficiency expressed through the lift-to-drag ratio, are presented. Next, the differences in the aerodynamic force coefficients for the different strut designs relative to the baseline no-strut wing configuration are evaluated. Finally, quantitative comparisons of the lift-to-drag ratio at $\alpha = 10^\circ$ are provided to directly assess the aerodynamic efficiency of the various strut designs and DEP propeller arrangements.

A. Comparisons of wing lift, drag, and lift-to-drag ratio against AoA.

Fig. 6 Comparisons of C_L , C_D , and C_L/C_D against α for all strut designs with propeller-off conditions at $V_\infty = 10$ m/s. Results shown for: (a) C_L against α , (b) C_D against α , and (c) C_L/C_D against α

The wing lift coefficient, C_L , and drag coefficient, C_D , are among the most substantial parameters for describing and comparing the aerodynamic characteristics of different configurations. These non-dimensional coefficients relate the aerodynamic forces acting on the wing to the freestream dynamic pressure and the wing reference area, and are governed by:

$$C_L = \frac{L}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V_\infty^2 S} \quad (4)$$

$$C_D = \frac{D}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V_\infty^2 S} \quad (5)$$

where L is the lift force, D is the drag force, ρ is the air density, V_∞ is the inflow velocity, and S is the wing reference area. The reference area S for different strut designs and DEP configurations is kept the same as the no-strut configuration in this study. Figure 6 shows the C_L , C_D , and C_L/C_D against α for propeller-off conditions, where propellers are removed during the test. It can be seen that Strut B and C slightly improve C_L of the wing for $\alpha > 10^\circ$, and delay the stall of the wing from $\alpha \approx 14^\circ$ to $\alpha \approx 16^\circ$. On the other hand, the drag of adding a strut increases in comparison to the no-strut wing in the propeller-off condition, with the longer strut, the higher the C_D because of the increased wetted area. The maximum C_L/C_D occurs at α between 8° and 10° , with a slight decrement in maximum C_L/C_D for strut-braced wings.

Fig. 7 Comparisons of C_L , C_D , and C_L/C_D against α for Case 1. Results shown for US-DEP configurations: (a) to (c) 12–12–12 configuration, and (d) to (f) 15–15–15 configuration.

In the current study, the lift and drag forces exerted on the wing are obtained by computing the load measurements from the overhead balance and the propeller thrust from the three load cells. Figure 7 illustrates the comparisons in wing C_L , C_D and C_L/C_D against α for US-DEP configurations in Case 1. Despite different rotational speeds for the 12- and 15-inch propellers, the C_L curves for both US-DEP configurations remain similar, and are comparatively insensitive to the strut design changes across the α sweep region. The difference in C_L for the 12–12–12 configuration with and without a strut is less than 5% for $\alpha < 15^\circ$. In contrast, C_D behaves differently between the two configurations. For the 12–12–12 configuration, Strut C design exhibits the highest drag among all other designs, while Strut A shows considerably lower C_D values, especially in the negative to low positive α regions. As a result, the wing aerodynamic efficiency, represented by the lift-to-drag ratio, is significantly improved from the Strut A design for non-zero wing AoAs from $-8^\circ < \alpha < 12^\circ$. In the high wing AoA region of $\alpha > 15^\circ$, this improvement in lift-to-drag ratio reduces. Moreover, Strut A advances the maximum C_L/C_D occurrence from $12^\circ \sim 14^\circ$ to $8^\circ \sim 10^\circ$. Both the Strut B and no-strut design for the 12–12–12 configuration demonstrated similar lift and drag performance for all α . For the 15–15–15 configuration, both Strut A and Strut B designs also experience a drag reduction compared to the Strut C and no-strut design, although the improvements in maximum C_L/C_D are not as significant as observed in the 12–12–12 configuration with the Strut

Fig. 8 Comparisons of C_L , C_D , and C_L/C_D against α for Case 1. Results shown for MS-DEP configurations: (a) to (c) 15–12–12 configuration, (d) to (f) 12–15–12 configuration, and (g) to (i) 12–12–15 configuration.

A configuration. The comparisons with propeller-off configurations (Fig. 6) indicate that the propeller-based DEP system is capable of significantly increasing the C_L over the wing, and further delays the stall occurrence, at the cost of increasing the drag simultaneously. The resulting maximum C_L/C_D is reduced compared to the propeller-off condition. Similar reductions in aerodynamic efficiency between propeller-off and propeller-on conditions have also been reported by recent numerical studies conducted by Sticchi et al. [28]. Thorough comparisons for quantitative C_L/C_D for different propeller arrangements and strut designs will be presented later in Section IV.C.

Figure 8 shows the comparisons in wing C_L , C_D and C_L/C_D against α for all three MS-DEP configurations operating in Case 1. In general, similar aerodynamic characteristics in C_L are observed to those of the US-DEP configurations in Fig. 7, with no significant improvements found across different strut designs. Strut A design demonstrates the lowest drag on the DEP system among all other designs, regardless of the position of the 15-inch propeller. For a 15-inch propeller placed at the outboard position (the 12–12–15 configuration), the drag is slightly lower than placing it at the inboard position (the 15–12–12 configuration), resulting in more favourable maximum C_L/C_D with Strut A design. With the 15-inch propeller placed at the middle between the two 12-inch propellers (the 12–15–12 configuration), both Strut A and Strut B designs exhibit substantial improvements in drag reduction and aerodynamic efficiency over the Strut C and no-strut designs. In addition, it can be noticed that for propeller arrangements with a middle 15-inch propeller (the 15–15–15 and 12–15–12 configuration), drag reduction can be achieved on both Strut A and Strut B designs, with the two strut designs demonstrating similar drag and efficiency performance in Case 1.

Figures 9 and 10 outline the same concepts of aerodynamic performance comparison for US-DEP and MS-DEP configurations in Case 2, where all propellers are operating at higher rotational speeds and thus higher slipstream speeds impacting on the wing and the strut surfaces. Overall, the lift curve slopes for US-DEP and MS-DEP configurations are steeper than those in Case 1. In addition, the pre-stall region seen at high α conditions ($\alpha > 15^\circ$) in Case 1 is delayed. As a result, the C_L curve retains linearity across the α sweep from -8° to 20° . The drag experienced

Fig. 9 Comparisons of C_L , C_D , and C_L/C_D against α for Case 2. Results shown for US-DEP configurations: (a) to (c) 12–12–12 configuration, and (d) to (f) 15–15–15 configuration.

Fig. 10 Comparisons of C_L , C_D , and C_L/C_D against α for Case 2. Results shown for MS-DEP configurations: (a) to (c) 15–12–12 configuration, (d) to (f) 12–15–12 configuration, and (g) to (i) 12–12–15 configuration.

on the DEP system also increases dramatically, overcoming the improvement in lift and reducing the aerodynamic efficiency in terms of lift-to-drag ratio in comparison to Case 1. The implementation of different strut designs also has insignificant effects on the wing C_L for all DEP configurations across the α sweep. Drag reduction can be observed for the 12–12–12 configuration with Strut A, and the 15–15–15 configuration with Strut B. Nonetheless, the improvements in aerodynamic efficiency with these strut designs are less significant than those achieved in Case 1. For the MS-DEP configurations shown in Fig. 10, the reductions in drag are slightly less than observed in Case 1. Among the three MS-DEP configurations, the 12–15–12 and 12–12–15 configurations show better Strut A drag reductions than the 15–12–12 configuration, and the 12–15–12 configuration also has favourable drag reduction and maximum C_L/C_D improvement for Strut B design.

B. Comparison of ΔC_L , ΔC_D and $\Delta(C_L/C_D)$ of different strut designs and DEP configurations.

Fig. 11 Comparisons of ΔC_L , ΔC_D , and $\Delta(C_L/C_D)$ relative to no-strut design against α for Case 1. Results shown for US-DEP configurations: (a) to (c) 12–12–12 configuration, and (d) to (f) 15–15–15 configuration.

Figure 11 illustrates the aerodynamic coefficient comparisons of the differences between Strut A, B and C relative to no-strut design for US-DEP configurations operating in Case 1, in terms of $\Delta C_L = C_L, with\ strut - C_L, no\ strut$, as an example. For both US-DEP configurations, the differences in ΔC_L across the three strut designs are not significant for $\alpha < 15^\circ$. In the high α region, minor improvements in C_L are observed for the wing with a strut compared to the wing without a strut. On the other hand, C_D exhibits noticeable differences across different strut designs. For the 12–12–12 configuration, Strut A design shows consistently lower drag than the wing without a strut. This reduction is more pronounced between $-8^\circ < \alpha < 15^\circ$. Strut B experiences similar drag to the no-strut configurations also in the region of $\alpha < 15^\circ$. The longest Strut C demonstrates the highest drag of all strut designs. As a result, C_L/C_D for Strut C is effectively reduced compared to no-strut configuration at all α (positive values of $\Delta C_L/C_D$ indicate reduced aerodynamic efficiency at negative α). In comparison, favourable improvements are observed in C_L/C_D for Strut A, reaching the greatest improvement of ~ 2 at $\alpha = 8^\circ$ compared to the no-strut design. Similar ΔC_L trends can also be found for the 15–15–15 configuration. Nonetheless, C_D reduction of Strut A is smaller than that in the 12–12–12 configuration, especially for $\alpha < 10^\circ$. The 15–15–15 configuration with Strut B design also provides similar drag reduction as the Strut A design. Consequently, both Strut A and B achieve similar C_L/C_D improvements in Case 1. Strut C has the highest drag among all strut designs under most α , resulting in reduced aerodynamic efficiency overall.

Figure 12 shows the same concepts of aerodynamic coefficient comparisons for MS-DEP configurations. The 15–12–12 and 12–15–12 configurations with Strut A have a slightly lower C_L than other strut designs for $\alpha < 8^\circ$. Similar to the US-DEP configurations, increments in C_L compared to the no-strut wing can be noticed at high α beyond 15° for most strut designs on all three MS-DEP configurations. For the 15–12–12 and the 12–12–15 configuration, Strut A exhibits consistently lower drag than other strut designs over the α sweep, whereas Strut B and C designs

Fig. 12 Comparisons of ΔC_L , ΔC_D , and $\Delta(C_L/C_D)$ relative to no-strut design against α for Case 1. Results shown for MS-DEP configurations: (a) to (c) 15–12–12 configuration, (d) to (f) 12–15–12 configuration, and (g) to (i) 12–12–15 configuration.

show similar trends. For the 12–15–12 configuration, the drag exerted on the wing for both Strut A and B designs is reduced compared to the no-strut design, whereas Strut C shows higher drag than the no-strut wing for most α . Consequently, both Strut A and B exhibit noticeable increments in C_L/C_D for the 12–15–12 configuration, while only substantial improvements with Strut A design are seen for the 15–12–12 and 12–12–15 configurations. For all MS-DEP configurations, Strut C exhibits the lowest C_L/C_D improvement across all strut designs.

Figure 13 compares ΔC_L , ΔC_D , and $\Delta(C_L/C_D)$ for both US-DEP configurations operating at the higher propeller rotational speed in Case 2. For both configurations, the differences in ΔC_L among the strut designs remain small up to $\alpha = 10^\circ$. Beyond this angle, Strut B begins to exhibit a higher C_L than Strut C. For the 12–12–12 configuration, Strut A yields the lowest C_D among all strut designs and, similar to the trends observed in Case 1, produces lower drag than the no-strut wing over most wing AoA. Strut B also achieves moderately lower C_D than the no-strut wing for $\alpha < 15^\circ$, whereas Strut C consistently generates higher drag than the no-strut design. In contrast, for the 15–15–15 configuration, all three strut designs exhibit lower drag than the no-strut wing within the range $0^\circ < \alpha < 10^\circ$, with Strut B providing the greatest drag reduction rather than Strut A. Consequently, all three strut designs demonstrate improved aerodynamic efficiency in terms of C_L/C_D , relative to the no-strut wing in the low positive AoA region.

Same comparisons for the MS-DEP configurations operating in Case 2 are presented in Figure 14. For both the 15–12–12 and 12–12–15 configurations, the differences in ΔC_L among the strut designs are small for $\alpha < 5^\circ$. Beyond $\alpha = 5^\circ$, Strut A in the 15–12–12 configuration and Strut B in the 12–12–15 configuration begin to produce higher C_L than the other two strut designs under most wing AoAs. The drag comparisons indicate that, among the three MS-DEP configurations, the 15–12–12 configuration exhibits the weakest drag reduction capability for both Strut A and Strut B under Case 2 operating conditions. As a result, the corresponding improvements in aerodynamic efficiency are also the smallest. By comparison, larger drag reduction, and therefore, higher C_L/C_D can be achieved by implementing Strut A and B to the 12–15–12 and 12–12–15 configurations. The 12–15–12 configuration with Strut B achieves greater drag

Fig. 13 Comparisons of ΔC_L , ΔC_D , and $\Delta (C_L/C_D)$ relative to no-strut design against α for Case 2. Results shown for US-DEP configurations: (a) to (c) 12-12-12 configuration, and (d) to (f) 15-15-15 configuration.

Fig. 14 Comparisons of ΔC_L , ΔC_D , and $\Delta (C_L/C_D)$ relative to no-strut design against α for Case 2. Results shown for MS-DEP configurations: (a) to (c) 15-12-12 configuration, (d) to (f) 12-15-12 configuration, and (g) to (i) 12-12-15 configuration.

reduction over the range $0^\circ < \alpha < 15^\circ$ than the 12–12–15 configuration using the same strut design, thereby resulting in a larger enhancement in C_L/C_D .

C. Comparison of C_L/C_D at $\alpha = 10^\circ$ for different strut designs and DEP configurations.

Fig. 15 Bar plot comparisons of $\frac{(C_L/C_D)}{(C_L/C_D)_{\text{no strut}}}$ at $\alpha = 10^\circ$ in percentage for different strut designs in Case 1 (left column) and Case 2 (right column). Results shown for US-DEP configurations: (a) and (b) 12–12–12 configuration, and (c) and (d) 15–15–15 configuration.

Figure 15 and 16 quantitatively compare the aerodynamic efficiency in C_L/C_D , for all three strut designs relative to the no-strut wing for all US- and MS-DEP configurations in Case 1 and Case 2 at $\alpha = 10^\circ$. The no-strut configuration is normalised to 100% in all cases. For the 12–12–12 configuration as shown in Fig. 15(a) and (b), Strut A produces the largest aerodynamic improvement in both operating cases, increasing the lift-to-drag ratio by around 29% and 15% relative to the no-strut wing. Strut B also improves C_L/C_D at this wing AoA, yielding around 7% – 9% increase, whereas Strut C results in a slight reduction of 2% – 4% compared to the no-strut wing. In contrast, both Strut A and Strut B on the 15–15–15 configuration exhibit only marginal improvements of approximately 3%, in Case 1, and around 10% in Case 2. Strut C provided a large reduction in C_L/C_D compared to the no-strut design in Case 1, and only slightly improved performance over the no-strut wing in Case 2.

Figure 16 presents the same C_L/C_D comparisons for different strut designs on the MS-DEP configurations. Overall, the 15–12–12 and the 12–12–15 configuration show similar trends: Strut A demonstrates significantly higher efficiency over other strut designs in Case 1, similar performance for both Strut A and B for Case 2, and Strut C has the lowest in both operating cases. More specifically, placing the 15-inch propeller at the outboard position yields even larger improvements in C_L/C_D at $\alpha = 10^\circ$, especially for Strut A design in Case 1, where an additional 10% improvement in C_L/C_D can be achieved by the 12–12–15 configuration than the 15–12–12 configuration. For the 12–15–12 configuration, the efficiency of having both Strut A and Strut B achieves dramatic increments in C_L/C_D compared to Strut C and no-strut wing, reaching more than 30% and 17% – 19% higher than the no-strut wing in Case 1 and 2, respectively. For all MS-DEP configurations, the Strut C design demonstrates similar performance to the no-strut configuration in Case 1, and a slight reduction in Case 2.

Figure 17 compares C_L/C_D for all US- and MS-DEP configurations relative to the 12–12–12 configuration for no-strut wing, Strut A, B and C designs in the two operating cases at $\alpha = 10^\circ$. In Case 1 (left column of Fig.17), the 15–15–15 configuration exhibits the highest aerodynamic efficiency compared to other propeller arrangements for the no-strut wing. The 15–12–12 and 12–15–12 configurations exhibit around 5% higher efficiency than the 12–12–12

Fig. 16 Bar plot comparisons of $\frac{(C_L/C_D)}{(C_L/C_D)_{\text{no strut}}}$ at $\alpha = 10^\circ$ in percentage for different strut designs in Case 1 (left column) and Case 2 (right column). Results shown for MS-DEP configurations: (a) and (b) 15–12–12 configuration, (c) and (d) 12–15–12 configuration, and (e) and (f) 12–12–15 configuration.

configuration. When Strut A is applied to the wing, the 12–15–12 and 12–12–15 configurations exhibit an increase in C_L/C_D relative to the 12–12–12 configuration, whereas the 15–15–15 and 15–12–12 configurations show a slight reduction. It should be noted that these comparisons are made based on DEP configurations with the Strut A design, which has already been demonstrated to provide better aerodynamic performance than other strut designs, as discussed previously. For Strut B, both 15–15–15 and 12–15–12 configurations demonstrate significant rises of around 16% and 30% in aerodynamic efficiency relative to the 12–12–12 configuration. All configurations exhibit better aerodynamic efficiencies than the 12–12–12 configuration when the longest Strut C is installed on the wing.

At the higher propeller rotational speeds in Case 2 (shown in the right column of Fig. 17), the aerodynamic behaviour is slightly different from Case 1, especially for the 15–15–15 configuration. In Case 2, the 15–15–15 configuration demonstrates less favourable aerodynamic efficiency than the 12–12–12 configuration with all strut designs except Strut C. The efficiency of the 15–12–12 configuration is also slightly reduced compared to the 12–12–12 configuration when a strut is installed, regardless of the strut length. In contrast, both 12–15–12 and 12–12–15 configurations show improved C_L/C_D performance compared to the 12–12–12 configuration. For Strut A and C, the improvements achieved by both configurations are similar, whereas for Strut B, the 12–15–12 configuration exhibits 6% higher efficiency than the 12–12–15 configuration, and 15% higher than the 12–12–12 configuration.

Overall, the aerodynamic performance of the strut-braced DEP system is strongly influenced by both the propeller arrangement and the installed strut design. Among the investigated configurations, the 12–15–12 configuration consistently demonstrates the most favourable aerodynamic efficiency, particularly when combined with Strut B where

Fig. 17 Bar plot comparisons of $\frac{(C_L/C_D)}{(C_L/C_D)_{12-12-12}}$ at $\alpha = 10^\circ$ in percentage for all US-DEP and MS-DEP configurations in Case 1 (left column) and Case 2 (right column). Results shown for: (a) and (b) no strut, (c) and (d) Strut A, (e) and (f) Strut B, and (g) and (h) Strut C.

the strut is directly mounted behind the middle 15-inch propeller. The 12–12–15 configuration also provides stable aerodynamic improvements for most strut designs and operating conditions. In contrast, the aerodynamic behaviour of the 15–15–15 configuration is highly dependent on the operating condition and strut designs, exhibiting large efficiency gains in Case 1 but reduced performance in Case 2 in general.

V. Numerical results.

With the initial experimental campaign completed, further analysis is conducted to form a numerical campaign. The results of which are demonstrated below. The goal of this is to provide insight into the flow behaviour and provide

Fig. 18 Simulation domain defined in the current work.

evidence for continued trends as seen in the experimental campaign. As such, a suitably sized domain is created for the simulation of the no-strut and Strut A design with the 12–12–12 configuration as shown in Fig. 18. This domain is of a suitable size relative to the wing span to allow the wake of the configuration to fully develop. Disk regions are defined within the mesh to allow for the actuator disk method described in III to be applied. The samples investigated are a set of eight evenly spaced angles of attack between $\alpha = -8^\circ$ and $\alpha = 20^\circ$. This provides a clean sweep of the domain, allowing for trends to be smoothly investigated.

A. Aerodynamic coefficients.

Fig. 19 Numerical comparisons of C_L and C_D against α for 12–12–12 configuration with no-strut and Strut A design. Results shown for: (a) and (b) Case 1, (c) and (d) Case 2.

Figure 19 focuses on the C_L and C_D variations for the 12–12–12 configuration with no-strut wing and Strut A design in both cases. Overall, the experimental and numerical results match well in the wing C_L curves for $\alpha < 15^\circ$, with the numerical simulations slightly underpredicting the lift compared to the experimental measurements. As observed in

the experimental results, the differences in C_L between no-strut and Strut A are small for most α in both cases. The Strut A design also demonstrates slightly lower drag than the no-strut configuration in Case 1 and 2, and the difference becomes more significant as α increases. It is noted that the drag is far lower than experimental results. This is due to two key reasons: firstly, the Euler formulation neglects viscous effects such as skin-friction drag, boundary-layer growth, and associated separation losses, so its predicted drag is expected to be substantially lower than experimental measurements. Furthermore, the actuator disk formulation directly adds momentum to the local flow, altering the pressure distribution over the surfaces. For low drag conditions, this can generate a sufficiently large pressure gradient to exceed the surface's unblown drag condition, and therefore can lead to negative drag. These two considerations lead to a sharp contrast between the drag measured from the experimental campaign and that calculated from the numerical campaign. Nonetheless, the low-fidelity results demonstrate the same trend as experimental data in this instance.

Fig. 20 Numerical comparisons of ΔC_L and ΔC_D against α for 12–12–12 configuration with Strut A design relative to no-strut wing for both cases. Results shown for: (a) ΔC_L , and (b) ΔC_D .

When inspecting the differences between the Strut A design and the no-strut wing for the 12–12–12 configuration in terms of ΔC_L and ΔC_D in both cases as shown in Fig. 20, a noted difference is observed. While both cases show reductions in drag coefficient, consistent with the experimental results, the Euler predictions differ in two respects. The numerical results indicate a much larger separation between Case 1 and Case 2, and they predict an increasing ΔC_D with α . Experimentally, the ΔC_D remains broadly similar between cases and instead decreases as α rises. This discrepancy is consistent with the inviscid Euler model neglecting viscous effects and boundary-layer separation, which become increasingly important at high angles of attack and under higher thrust conditions.

Despite the limitations inherent to the low-fidelity approach, the results provide strong evidence supporting the validity of the experimental observations, namely that a strut-supported configuration can outperform an equivalent configuration without a strut. These findings therefore justify the use of the low-fidelity Euler methodology as an investigative tool for examining the spanwise lift and drag distributions presented in the following section.

B. Spanwise lift and drag distributions.

The spanwise lift distribution for the 12–12–12 configuration with Strut A at different α in both cases is illustrated in Fig. 21. The lift distribution trends in both cases are as expected; as α pitches up, spanwise lift increases in a steady manner with consistent spacing between results. The propeller hub positions are marked on the graphs with a black dashed, vertical line. Within these regions, an elevated lift force is seen, which is expected due to the blowing of the propellers over the wing. There is a sharp lift gradient through these lines; these are representative of regions where the swirl of the propeller dominates the flow, modifying the local flow incidence with the wing and therefore impacting lift distribution. This interpretation is supported by the fact that these gradients are much higher in Case 2 (see Fig.21 (b)) than in Case 1. In addition, there is a noticeable discontinuity between the spanwise location of 0.4 m and 0.5 m. This discontinuity is due to the spanwise surface slicing; the wing-strut connection is parallel to the slicing plane and therefore cannot be easily parsed by this method. As such, the strut connection region shows a non-physical discontinuity within the plot. From inspecting the spanwise lift distribution, it is also clear that the propellers rotating at 6500 rpm in Case 2 have a significantly greater impact on the lift than the 4000 rpm propellers in Case 1, with larger uniform steps between the sampled wing AoA.

Figure 22 presents the spanwise drag distribution for the 12–12–12 configuration with the no-strut wing and the

Fig. 21 Numerical lift distribution along the wing span for 12–12–12 configuration with Strut A design for α from -8° to 20° . Results shown for: (a) Case 1, and (b) Case 2. Dashed black lines represent the propeller hub locations.

Fig. 22 Numerical drag distribution along the wing span for 12–12–12 configuration with Strut A design at $\alpha = 12^\circ$. Results shown for: (a) Case 1, and (b) Case 2. Dashed black lines represent the propeller hub locations.

Strut A design operating under Cases 1 and 2 at $\alpha = 12^\circ$. The numerical drag distributions further support the trends observed experimentally. In the region upstream of the strut discontinuity, the Strut A configuration exhibits a substantially lower drag than the no-strut wing for both operating cases. Although it has previously been noted that Euler simulations coupled with actuator disk models can produce non-physical negative drag values, the observed drag reduction within the strut region cannot be attributed solely to limitations of the low-fidelity modelling approach. This interpretation is reinforced by the drag behaviour in the region beyond the strut-wing joint towards the wingtip, where the spanwise drag distributions for the no-strut wing and the Strut A configuration become nearly identical. If the discrepancy were primarily caused by model fidelity, a more global deviation in the drag distribution would be expected. Instead, the localised drag reduction upstream of the strut-wing connection strongly suggests that it arises from the aerodynamic interaction between the strut and the propeller. Nevertheless, the exact cause of this consistent shift in the drag distribution requires further investigations of the simulation solutions.

C. Pressure contours on the strut surface.

Fig. 23 Contour plots of pressure coefficient difference ΔC_P relative to propeller-off conditions on the upper surface of Strut A for the 12–12–12 configuration at $\alpha = 12^\circ$. Results shown for: (a) Case 1, and (b) Case 2.

To validate the Strut A performance gains relevant to the no-strut configuration the surface flow changes induced by the propellers must be isolated. Particularly for the strut region, as highlighted within the spanwise distributions. A comparison case is run with the actuator disk source terms removed; this is referred to as the ‘propeller-off’ condition. The intention of this comparison is to identify the mechanism responsible for the drag reduction as seen from global coefficients and from the spanwise distributions. Whilst the strut region has been identified as the principal source of drag reduction, the cause of this behaviour remains to be established. Thus, comparing surface pressure coefficients for the blown and unblown cases, it is possible to separate the propeller-driven contributions from the geometry. The interest is taken to observe a reduction in pressure coefficient along the strut leading edge, as shown in Fig. 23. In the figure, the changes in surface pressure coefficients relative to the propeller-off condition, ΔC_P , for both Case 1 and Case 2 are visualised. Both cases show a clear reduction in ΔC_P , but the evidence of propeller-strut aerodynamic coupling is more visible in Case 2. The decrease occurs within the regions in the propeller slipstream, particularly within the strut wing connection and along the strut leading edge. The effect weakens towards the wing root, consistent with the dissipating influence of the slipstream in that region. This links the local blowing directly to the observed drag reduction and indicates that the coupling strengthens as propeller RPM and therefore thrust increases from Case 1 to Case 2.

It is important to reinforce that while this narrative follows the numerical campaign with regards to identifying and analysing the source of the drag reduction, there are expected differences between numerical and experimental results. This is due to the inherent limitations of the Euler approach. The Euler approach can only feasibly identify pressure contributions, and thus why the ΔC_P is analysed for highlighting drag reduction. A more complex analysis is required to investigate the viscous contribution to drag. However, the results demonstrated throughout the numerical campaign clearly demonstrate fundamental aerodynamic coupling between the propellers and strut. What is required is a further investigation on how the more complex flow physics may influence the numerical results, potentially bringing them more in line to those seen from the experimental campaign.

VI. Conclusions.

This study experimentally and numerically investigates the aerodynamic characteristics of strut-braced DEP systems with different strut designs and propeller arrangements. Three strut designs and five propeller arrangements for a leading-edge-mounted triple-propeller DEP system were examined at two propeller rotational speeds. The struts were designed with different lengths and were placed between the inboard and mid propellers, directly behind the mid propeller, and between the mid and outboard propellers, with the same vertical length. The experimental results show that the shortest strut design (Strut A) can significantly reduce the wing drag, even below that of the corresponding no-strut wing configuration. This drag reduction is more pronounced at the lower propeller rotational speed, with improvements of up to 30% achieved for the most promising configuration. Comparisons among the five propeller arrangements indicate that the combination of one centrally mounted 15-inch propeller and two adjacent 12-inch propellers generally provides the most favourable aerodynamic efficiency in terms of the wing lift-to-drag ratio for the strut-braced DEP wings.

A preliminary numerical investigation was conducted to identify the mechanism responsible for the observed drag reduction. The low-fidelity Euler-based analysis enabled rapid evaluation of the tested configurations and indicated that strut-equipped arrangements can achieve lower drag coefficients than equivalent strut-free cases. Spanwise drag analysis further showed that the reduction was localised within the strut-braced region and increased with propeller thrust, suggesting a strong aerodynamic interaction between the propeller slipstream and the strut geometry. Although limited in fidelity, the numerical results support the experimental observations and indicate that the proposed drag-reduction mechanisms are physically plausible. While this behaviour was reproduced for the Strut A design, this does not necessarily imply that the results for the Strut B and C designs are invalid. The Euler-based approach neglects viscous effects, and it is therefore possible that, with increasing strut length, viscous drag becomes the dominant contribution. Additional higher-fidelity analysis is required to assess this hypothesis and further quantify the underlying flow physics.

Based on these findings, future studies should focus on experimental flow-field visualisation, particularly in the strut region, to deepen understanding of the interactions among the propeller slipstream, the wing, and the strut surfaces. The next step for the numerical simulations will be to increase the simulation fidelity. This will first involve adopting an Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) approach to more accurately capture viscous effects and boundary-layer separation. Subsequently, an actuator-line methodology will be implemented to represent the propeller. The combination of URANS and actuator-line modelling will enable the concentrated effects of the propeller slipstream to be resolved in a time-accurate manner. Extending these additional experimental and numerical approaches to the remaining strut designs and DEP configurations will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the flow-field interactions in propeller-based strut-braced DEP systems.

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